

Defining the prototyping space to support the innovation process with fablabs

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Abstract

Among the different roles that can be assigned to fablabs, the one of a prototyping place to support InnovationLab is recurrent. In this context, the prototyping activity can take a broad scope, covering different phases of the innovation process, from problem definition and customer validation to project development. As a consequence, the role of fabmanagers extends to the one of prototyping coach. The projects supported can be products as well as services and the people may not be pure maker profiles. Therefore, it seems appropriate to develop a global vision for prototyping that encompasses these different situations, promoting the posture “How can I start making my project with the available resources?”

Here, we propose to explore the potential of transposing a model from human-computer interaction (Houde & Hill, 1997) (Yang, 2005) to the field of design sciences. The model intends to separate design issues into the “role”, the “look and feel” and the “implementation” axes. In order to better understand the meaning of each axis, we propose an adaptation of the model and an evaluation method to position the prototype on the different axes. The “role” focuses on the integration of the context, the interactions and the target audiences associated to a project. The “look and feel” supports the need to represent the project from a rough sketch that supports the visualization of an idea to a well-defined project that can be properly assembled, it defines “how the project will look like”. The “implementation” axis targets the technical aspects of the project, it helps to drive the technical development of the project: “how the project works”.

The model has been tested on a first series of entrepreneurial projects. For instance, in the process of developing a tool to unbend pylons, we created a prototype of pylon with adapted characteristics justified by the need to clarify the problem. On one hand, being able to position the prototype on this model helped the participant to better understand the process they were involved in. On the other hand, understanding the model characteristics helped to define the prototyping effort regardless of the technical feasibility nor the look and feel of the solution.

From this, we explicitate the aforementioned axis with different case studies to clarify their benefits from other prototyping compasses.

Keywords

prototyping, fablabs, innovation

1 Introduction

Among the different roles that can be assigned to fablabs, the one of a place dedicated to prototyping to support InnovationLabs (Troxler 2010) is recurrent. InnovationLabs aim at supporting the innovation journey of their audiences: researchers, entrepreneurs, institutions, private companies or public

associations with processes mostly inspired from design thinking: having a strong focus on first hand experimentation through prototyping, giving sense to the fablabs facilities associated to the place.

When it comes to prototyping, the makers community hosted in fablabs comes in addition to the equipment available in fablabs. This community can be characterized by a “making do with what is at hand” behavior (Baker 2005) with core principles extracted from the DIY movement (Camburn 2015) and their design practices. Another trait of the maker movement that contributes to their efficiency in prototyping is the openness promoted by the Fablab’s charter (The Fab charter, n.d), with numerous open-source repository platform consolidating the global know-how, providing reference materials, both hardware and software, for makers to make almost anything.

InnovationLabs host all sorts of project at different phase of innovation processes (Furr 2014). In addition to project-specific workflows suggested implicitly by the nature of the project, we also consider the status of the project as well as its classes of development model (i.e. as technology push, market demand (Bishop 2004) or user innovation (Bruns 2014)). The challenge for the InnovationLabs is to provide these resources with a framework that will make them able to support the projects with adequate prototyping practices.

First of all, there are different definitions of prototyping, some make distinctions between a functional prototype and various representation, like models and mock-ups, that will lead to it (Herman 2011). In this paper we assume the more inclusive definition from Lim (Lim 2008): “Prototyping is an activity with the purpose of creating a manifestation that, in its simplest form, filters the qualities in which designers are interested, without distorting the understanding of the whole”. One interesting aspect of this definition is that it doesn’t limit prototyping to the creation of an object but opens it to a broader interpretation.

Various models can be found in the literature to define the different roles of prototyping. They can be classified based either on their objectives (i.e. Active learning, exploration, communication or refinement (Camburn 2017)) or on the form they take (i.e. visual prototype, proof of concept, presentation prototype (Ulman 2010)). When it comes to selecting the right prototyping activity, another part of literature covers strategic aspects of prototyping dedicated to support divergence and convergence in a design space through iterations (Camburn 2015) (Bushnell 2013), how to filters the characteristics of interest in a prototype (Lim 2008), but also propose techniques that intend to validate the customer interest for the project being developed: minimum viable product, Turkish automat... (Savoia 2005).

Prototyping is manifold considering the numerous variables required to reach a successful process: the purpose of the prototype, the strategy to reach your objective, the techniques to materialize the project. Each aspect being considered with a will to optimize the resources invested regarding time, manpower and materials.

In this paper, we propose to design a tool guiding the prototyping activity among the plethora of available options that can be valid in the different forms of innovation processes?

2 State of the art

In this section we present a couple of models from the literature that look to answer the question with their advantage and limitations. The selected model will support the latter stage of this work.

2.1 The technical readiness level (TRL) scale (Mankins 1995)

The technology readiness level scale was developed by the NASA as a systematic metric that support the assessment of the functional maturity of a particular technology and is widely adopted as a standardized process to manage the timing and budget risks of a new technological development. The levels presented in Table 1 are associated with information regarding the cost level and categories of activities. They propose a qualitative description of what level of functionality should be targeted for each level.

TRL	Definition
0	Nothing defined
1	Basic principles observed and reported
2	Technology concept and/or application formulated
3	Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof-of-concept
4	Component and/or breadboard validation in laboratory environment
5	Component and/or breadboard validation in relevant environment
6	System/sub-system model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment
7	System prototype demonstration in an operational environment
8	Actual system completed and “flight qualified” through test and demonstration
9	Actual system “flight proven” through successful mission operations

Table 1 - NASA technology readiness level scale (Mankins, 1995)

When it comes to answering our question, the benefit of this scale is that it proposes a straightforward path to develop a project following a sequence from first proposing and validating a concept, then assembling an experimental proof of concept and next integrating component aspects to turn the technology into a product.

The weakness of this model is that it may be too rigid: questions about the form of the project and the environment in which it will evolve only coming from level 4. There have been discussions about the challenges of using the TRLs to fully manage a new technological development process (Olechowski 2020). We support the argumentation that it should only be considered as a technology maturity assessment tool and is not intended to challenge other aspects associated to the human perception of the project like opportunity, usability or desirability of the project.

2.2 The hierarchical morphological prototyping (HMP) taxonomy (Stove 2009)

The hierarchical morphological prototyping taxonomy aims at describing prototypes as a design representation which enable designers to communicate, test or validate design ideas with a classification that is independent from the design goals. To this end, it describes a prototype in term of variety: either physical or non-physical. In term of relative complexity: the prototype can be about one of its components, sub-systems or about the entire system. And finally, in term of fidelity which represent the level of realism the prototype represents from its simplest form to its final representation.

This representation benefits from classifying prototypes with early design representations that would not be traditionally considered as prototypes, such as sketches. Another positive aspect is that it offers a clear progression path to characterize the level of completion associated to a project: from nothing to sketch, to CAD, to actual parts. In term of complexity, the effort goes from identifying the different components, to working on sub-systems to finally develop a full system. And in term of fidelity, we can clearly support the reflection from the early form of the project, to the final manufactured parts.

One of the weaknesses of this representation is the absence of a consolidated vision to support the technical development of a project. Furthermore, by design, this representation weakly considers interactions aspects of the prototype with its environment and users leaving these aspects to the interpretation of the designer.

2.3 The triangle model of ‘what prototype prototypes’ (Houde and Hill, 1997)

The triangle model of ‘what prototype prototypes’ represented in Figure 1 proposes a referential covering more than just the technical and material aspects of the prototyping activity that tend to be overlooked by others more engineering oriented. This model is intended to support human computer interactions,

but can be of interest when it comes to integrating interactions with users and or environment (Yang 2005). In this model, each corner of the triangle represents a different purpose of a prototype

- The “Implementation”, concerns the ability of a prototype to perform its intended functions and therefore how the project works.
- The “Look and feel”, is about the information relative to the form and appearance of a design defining how the project will look like.
- The “Role”, intends to provide information regarding the use as well as the context of use associated with the prototype, defining if and how the project will be used.

To validate the applicability of this model to physical prototypes, Hernley (Hernley 2011) positioned different prototypes on this triangle, one of the outcomes was the difficulty to distinguish the purpose of some design questions. Since there was no clear characterization of the different categories, the position on the triangle was open for different interpretations.

Figure 1 – The triangle prototype classification model (Houde 1997) represents four principal categories of prototypes. Implementation, it is all about validating that a design is able to perform its intended function and therefore how the project works. Look and feel, is about the information relative to the form and appearance of a design defining how the project will look like. Role, intend to provide information relative to the use and context of use associated to a project defining if and how the project will be used.

In the next section of this paper, we elaborate this triangle model in order to clarify how prototypes fit in the different categories.

3 An iteration on the triangle model: a proposal for improvement

The first characteristic of interest associated to the triangle model is that it considers prototyping as a more global activity that just targeting a product as a technological assembly: it includes questioning the role of the project itself.

Another motivation to elaborate on the triangle model is the visual support associated to the model and the potential message it can convey. In this section we describe the approach followed to develop the visualization support and then how we structure our model for the message to be efficient.

3.1 The data visualization support

The starting point is to improve the data visualization efficiency. The main ingredients in a graphical representation is to have a clear purpose, provide a clear visualization of the data and making the message transported by the visualization obvious (Vandemeulebroecke 2019).

In the presented situation, the purpose is twofold, one is to characterize a prototype in regards of its intended objective, the second is to highlight the next iterations opportunities.

The first step is to choose the right tool to support the communication of the proposed model. The support identified is a radar chart visualization, it enables to visualize different characteristics of a prototype and allows the comparisons of different prototypes to each other (Seide 2020).

To provide a clear visualization of the data and to support the communication of the messages conveyed, a radar chart combines several useful properties. The Circular x-axis is defined by the 3 categories (Role, Implementation and look and feel), then to characterize a prototype, the distance from center are set on the y-axis for each characteristic defining the different categories. The different values for the y axis are normalized. The objective is to inform on the relative sense of completion associated to different prototypes and highlight the challenge to develop on the next iterations. A range of 0 represents no information associated to a category, while a range of 1 represents the maximum level possible associated. Figure 2 give an example of representation on how the radar chart representation of the triangle model could look like for a role-oriented prototype.

Figure 2 – A radar chart example representation for the model, the Circular x-axis is defined by the 3 categories (Role, Implementation and look and feel), the distance from center are set on the y-axis for each characteristic defining the different categories. The axes are normalized to represent the relative completion of a prototype.

The next sections of this chapter aim at clarifying the different characteristics associated to these categories. To support the reflection when it comes to defining the next iterations, we propose a way to scale the characterization of the prototype in order to give a sense of relative completion for the different characteristics of a prototype.

3.2 Defining an ‘Implementation’ scale

The message associated to the ‘Implementation’ category covers the aspects of prototypes aiming at validating that a design is able to perform its intended function and therefore “how the project will work”. The technology readiness level scale, presented in section 2.1, is meant to support these aspects of prototyping. As discussed, it covers the technological maturity assessment of a technology and should limit to these aspects according to some.

From the table 1, we can see that the first technical readiness levels are independent from the components and/or environment associated to the final version of the project. From level 4, these aspects start to be considered, making room for the fourth category defined in the triangle model: The Integration category, that starts to address prototypes covering more than one single purpose.

As expected from the purpose of this model, we can clearly position the functional readiness level of the project and anticipate what would be the objective associated to the next readiness level avoiding to target too much too fast. It also leaves the opportunity to develop on the other categories of the prototype either role or look and feel based on the project needs.

3.3 Defining a ‘Look and feel’ scale

The message associated to the ‘Look and feel’ category covers the aspects of prototypes aiming to characterize the level of information regarding the product assembly, from the first sketch to the final product Bill of material, or “how the project will look like”. In order to cover these aspects of a prototype, we consider the taxonomic hierarchy proposed by Stove and described in section 2.2 as adequate.

In this case, an effort is required to convert this taxonomy into a scale. We begin with the fact that by definition, these three characteristics are considered as orthogonal following this taxonomy. Next, per characteristics we rank each definition based on the level information associated, from the lowest level of information to the highest level of completion. Based on these hypotheses, we propose to compute the HMP score as the product of the weight associated to each characteristic (Figure 3). With a score ranging from 0 to a maximum of 24, we can give a relative sense of completions between different prototypes and positions it on the ‘Look and feel’ scale.

$$\text{Score} = \begin{array}{|l|l|} \hline \text{Variety} & \\ \hline \text{Physical} & 2 \\ \text{Non-Physical} & 1 \\ \text{No representation} & 0 \\ \hline \end{array} \times \begin{array}{|l|l|} \hline \text{Complexity} & \\ \hline \text{System} & 3 \\ \text{Sub-system} & 2 \\ \text{Component} & 1 \\ \hline \end{array} \times \begin{array}{|l|l|} \hline \text{Fidelity} & \\ \hline \text{Realistic} & 4 \\ \text{Detailed} & 3 \\ \text{Basic} & 2 \\ \text{Form} & 1 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Figure 3: HMP Score – The HMP score is the product of each of the prototype’s look and feel characteristic weight from the lowest level of information to the highest level of completion.

Following this scale, the lowest scores may be independent from the other categories. But at some point, there is a need to integrate functional parts in the prototype and/or use it to challenge its intended role. These later prototypes would be associated to the Integration category.

As expected from the purpose of this model, we can clearly position the prototype in term of completion of the product definition, but also set objective for the next iterations either developing on the ‘look and feel’ and the manufacturing aspects or developing on the implementation or role aspect of the prototype.

3.4 Defining a ‘Role’ scale

When it comes to defining the role, it’s not as straightforward as for the other categories. The motivation to characterize the role comes from the Design Thinking process and its user-oriented approach supported by observation and testing (Mueller-Roterberg, C. 2018), we want to cover prototypes that challenges if and how the project will be used. Among the different things we can observe, we can extract three global characteristics on which we can have some control when setting up a prototype for observation:

- The context for the project that represents the environment and conditions in which the project should take place.
- The target audience that represents the project end user.
- The interactions that represent the level of interactions between the target audience and the prototype.

When prototyping, the context can either be none, simulated or real. Depending on the situation, it may be considered as not necessary to be considered and therefore supporting the prototyping activity with “none” aspects of the context. A “simulated” context may be useful when the actual context is too

restrictive to be constructive, in this case the simulation may be associated with simplifications. Eventually, the “real” context of use is the situation with the lowest number of hypothesis.

When selecting an audience for a prototyping setup, the quality of the feedback may vary depending on your audience. “Family, friends and foes” may be too biased to critic. “Random people” may not be involved enough to generate a constructive feedback. A “selected target audience” should provide educated insights. A larger “extended target audience” should provide information from a broader spectrum of the target audience, from the first-time buyers to the non-buyers.

Finally, the level of interactions proposed with the setup raises the level of the user experience and therefore the level of information we can collect. The minimum level we can expect is to for the end-user to be able to “listen and/or see” the prototyping setup. Then, one of the first motivation for prototyping is to be able to “touch” and make a first-hand impression on the project. The next level is to be able to “interact following the lead” of instructions that guarantee the experience. Finally, the most advanced level of experience is for the tester to interact “on its own” in similar conditions to the one associated to the end product.

To convert this characterization into a scale, we use the same principle as for the Look and feel. Per characteristic, we associate to each definition a weight from the lowest level of information to the highest one and we multiply the three weights together as shown on figure 4.

Figure 4: Role Score – The Role score is the product of each of the prototype’s role characteristic weight from the lowest level of information to the highest level of completion. The context for the project that represents the environment and conditions in which the project should take place. The target audience that represents the project end user. The interactions that represent the level of interactions between the target audience and the prototype.

The score may range from 0 to 48, allowing to sort the different combinations from the less representative to a real-life full-scale prototype. In the early stage of a project, this scale may be independent from the other one, the purpose of such prototype is to help to assess the problem statement. But quickly, it will be associated to either elements of functionality or look and feel to support practical validations of the project.

4 Use cases

In this section, we discuss a couple of cases with specific profiles, explain how the radar supported the prototyping activity and highlighted the next prototyping steps.

4.1 Use case 1: pylon unbending

In this first case study, the long-term objective is to develop a mechanical tool to unbend pylons for an electricity system operator company in Belgium. The sole information to start was that pylons get damaged. A first workshop was planned with different work-profiles coming both from the electrical company and the university’s engineering department. The intention was to follow a prototyping approach to tackle the challenge.

Based on this, there was nothing to prototype from a functionality point of view since there was no technical concept identified to meet the objective and it was the same from a look and feel perspective. The remaining option was to focus on the role category.

Looking at the characteristics that define the role, we already had “the selected target audience” booked for the workshop. In order to stimulate the interactions as much as possible, the reflection focused on the context. ‘No context’ would not allow interactions as there would be nothing to manipulate. A ‘real context’ prototype would not be much constructive either because too restrictive, the human and technological resources required to deform a real pylon are out of practical reach.

Therefore, we prototyped a “simulated context” with a similar shape to the real life. We relaxed the constraints by choosing a thinner and more deformable structural parts in order to make manipulations and “interactions following the lead” of a coach possible, but still looked for the parts behavior to be representative of a stronger one. The prototype developed and its associated chart can be seen on figure 5.

Figure 5 – (Left) a Radar chart of the pylon unbending prototype workshop: Role score = 2 (Context simulated) x 3 (Selected target audience) x 3 (Interactions following the lead) / 48 (for normalization) = 0.375 (Right) picture of the context prototype associated, a pylon prototype made of thinner structural parts to make manipulations possible.

The workshop was considered as a success by the different stakeholders, the prototype allowed a lot of manipulations, the fablab environment provided a lot of tools to quickly explore and challenge ideas. From an implementation point of view, we had formulated a promising technology concept (TRL 2) that could be able to answer the challenge. The next steps were also clear, from an implementation point of view, there was a need to validate the hypothesis that the proposed concept would work in the nominal situation of a real size pylon. The first test would be to perform a similar manipulation on isolated pylon structural parts. From a Look and feel point of view, it was already possible to envision a ‘basic-system-physical’ prototype to evaluate practical aspect of the tool, like interactions with the pylon or handling conditions.

4.2 Use case 2: OSBricks

The OSBricks project’s objective is to create a brick from a wood plank intended to be filled with insulation rags or old clothes to create an insulated wall.

Considering the triangle, we have three options to elaborate the concept: the “Implementation”, the “Look and feel” or the “role” scale. To develop on the role would be a possibility: to explore the interest and feasibility for peoples to gather enough materials to fill in the bricks will be something to validate in the future next steps of the project. But in this case, to develop on the look and feel of the project seemed an easier path to follow.

Since it was the first attempt to concretize the project, it was important to be as flexible as possible when selecting the fabrication technique. Picking the laser cutter to create this first set of basic-system-physical prototypes allowed to quickly iterate on the first design and fix firsts design issues (cf. Figure 6) that were already obvious despite the basic level of fidelity offered by the scale down.

Figure 6 – Radar chart of the OSBrick prototype: TRL score = 0,2: Technology concept formulated / HMP score = 2 (physical) x 3 (product) x 2 (basic) / 24 (for normalization) = 0,5 and picture of the different iterations realized at this step. (it. 1, it. 2, it 3)

Once the laser cut design was approved, the design effort was minimal to create a first set of real size bricks with a CNC router. The two manufacturing techniques are similar and the design constraints could be anticipated at the laser cutting stage.

With a full-size, CNC cut prototype, we have a potential product in hand, but there is still a need to demonstrate its efficiency or its usability by elaborating on the other categories of the model.

5 Conclusion and prospective

This paper proposes a model to characterize the prototyping activity in its larger definition, from discussed sketch to approved product, developing on different other models in an attempt to structure the prototyping planning of whatever project that could be proposed to a maker.

On a couple of use cases, we have described how clarifying the characteristics of the different categories of prototypes helped to set up a prototyping strategy for the situation proposed.

At this stage, the model can still be developed. Some definitions may be consolidated or refined. The scoring method may be improved to avoid equivalent score for different combination. It has to be challenged on situations such as for complex system with different level of completion for different part

of the system. The visualization support may be extended to highlight the characteristics of each categories.

Another potential development for this work is to associate standardized radar chart profiles to different prototyping techniques (serious play,) or different stages (problem definition, ideation, customer validation, incubation...) and situations (communications, observations, testing...) of a project development. Such consolidation would support the model's intention to not tempt the project owner to reach complete scale in one step, but rather to iterate, setting the prototyping objectives to the right amount of effort in order to optimize the resources and minimize wasted effort.

Finally, to be coherent with the model, another point of interest is the adherence of other InnovationLab's to this model as a tool to support their prototyping activity.

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References

- Baker, T., & Nelson, R. E. (2005). Creating something from nothing: Resource construction through entrepreneurial bricolage. *Administrative science quarterly*, 50(3), 329-366.
- Bishop, G. L., & Magleby, S. P. (2004, January). A review of technology push product development models and processes. In *International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference* (Vol. 46962, pp. 383-392).
- Bruns, A. (2014). Media innovations, user innovations, societal innovations. *The journal of media innovations*, 1(1), 13-27.
- Bushnell, T., Steber, S., Matta, A., Cutkosky, M., & Leifer, L. (2013, September). Using a 'Dark Horse' prototype to manage innovative teams. In *3rd International Conference on Integration of Design, Engineering and Management for Innovation* (p. 8).
- Camburn, B. A., Jensen, D., Crawford, R., Otto, K., & Wood, K. (2015). Evaluation of a strategic method to improve prototype performance with reduced cost and fabrication time. In *DS 80-4 Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Engineering Design (ICED 15) Vol 4: Design for X, Design to X, Milan, Italy, 27-30.07. 15* (pp. 333-342).
- Camburn, B. A., Sng, K. H., Perez, K. B., Otto, K., Wood, K. L., Jensen, D., & Crawford, R. (2015, August). The way makers prototype: principles of DIY design. In *International Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference* (Vol. 57175, p. V007T06A004). American Society of Mechanical Engineers.
- Camburn, B., Viswanathan, V., Linsey, J., Anderson, D., Jensen, D., Crawford, R., ... & Wood, K. (2017). Design prototyping methods: state of the art in strategies, techniques, and guidelines. *Design Science*, 3.
- Furr, N., & Dyer, J. (2014). Choose the right innovation method at the right time. *Harvard Business Review*, 12.
- Herman, B., Sapin, J., Tran Duy, K., & Raucent, B. (2011). On the types and roles of demonstrators for designing medical devices. In *DS 68-9: Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Engineering Design (ICED 11), Impacting Society through Engineering Design, Vol. 9: Design Methods and Tools pt. 1, Lyngby/Copenhagen, Denmark, 15.-19.08. 2011* (pp. 101-110).
- Hernley, L. R. (2011). An analysis of early stage prototypes using implementation, look and feel, and role (Doctoral dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology)
- Houde, S., & Hill, C. (1997). What do prototypes prototype? In *Handbook of human-computer interaction* (pp. 367-381). North-Holland.
- Lim, Y. K., Stolterman, E., & Tenenber, J. (2008). The anatomy of prototypes: Prototypes as filters, prototypes as manifestations of design ideas. *ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI)*, 15(2), 1-27.
- Mankins, J. C. (1995). Technology readiness levels. *White Paper*, April, 6(1995), 1995
- Mankins, J. C. (2009). Technology readiness assessments: A retrospective. *Acta Astronautica*, 65(9-10), 1216-1223.

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- Mueller-Roterberg, C. (2018). Handbook of design thinking. Hochschule Ruhr West.
- Olechowski, A. L., Eppinger, S. D., Joglekar, N., & Tomaschek, K. (2020). Technology readiness levels: Shortcomings and improvement opportunities. *Systems Engineering*, 23(4), 395-408.
- Savoia, A. (2011). Pretotype it. Make sure you are building the right it before you build it right.
- Seide, S. E., Jensen, K., & Kieser, M. (2021). Utilizing radar graphs in the visualization of simulation and estimation results in network meta-analysis. *Research synthesis methods*, 12(1), 96-105.
- Stowe, D. T. (2009). Investigating the role of prototyping in mechanical design using case study validation (Doctoral dissertation, Clemson University).
- The Fab Charter. (n.d.). Retrieved September 6, 2022, from <http://fab.cba.mit.edu/about/charter/>
- Troxler, P., & Wolf, P. (2010). Bending the rules: the fab lab innovation ecology.
- Ullman, D. G. (2010). The mechanical design process: Part 1.
- Vandemeulebroecke, M., Baillie, M., Margolskee, A., & Magnusson, B. (2019). Effective visual communication for the quantitative scientist. *CPT: pharmacometrics & systems pharmacology*, 8(10), 705-719.
- Yang, M. C. (2005). A study of prototypes, design activity, and design outcome. *Design Studies*, 26(6), 649-669.